
EFFECT OF SUSTAINABLE CLIMATE FINANCE ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study examined the effect of Sustainable Climate Finance on Economic Development in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to; examine the effect of Private sector mobilization on Economic Development in Nigeria. Evaluate the international mobilization on Economic Development in Nigeria. A quantitative research design was adopted for the study. A structured questionnaire, design with a 5-point Likert scale was use to collect data for the study. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis. The result review that Private sector mobilization has a significant effect on Economic Development with a coefficient value of .462 with p-value (0.000). International mobilization has a significant effect on Economic Development a coefficient value of .347 with p-value (0.000) in Nigeria. The study concluded that Sustainable Climate Finance has significant effect on Economic Development in Nigeria. The study recommended that the government should develop policies that provide tax incentives, subsidies, and grants to encourage private sector investment in renewable energy and sustainable projects.*

Keywords: *Climate, Development, Economic, Finance, Sustainable*

1.1 Introduction

Sustainable climate finance is a critical component in the global effort to address climate change and its associated impacts (World Bank. 2023). As the urgency to combat climate change intensifies, financial mechanisms that support sustainable development and climate resilience are increasingly recognized as essential (Zattler, 2024). Sustainable climate finance refers to investments and funding directed towards projects and initiatives that aim to mitigate climate change, adapt to its effects, and promote sustainable development (OECD 2023). This includes financing renewable energy projects, energy efficiency improvements, sustainable agriculture, and other initiatives that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance climate resilience (OECD 2023). The importance of sustainable climate finance lies in its potential to catalyze the transition to a low-carbon economy. It enables countries, especially developing ones, to invest in sustainable infrastructure, enhance their adaptive capacity, and ultimately contribute to global climate goals, such as those outlined in the Paris Agreement (Kshetri, 2022).

Sustainable climate finance has emerged as a pivotal mechanism for fostering economic development while addressing the pressing challenges of climate change. In Nigeria, a country characterized by its rich natural resources and diverse ecosystems, the integration of sustainable climate finance into economic planning is crucial (Myint, and Krueger, 2025). As Nigeria grapples with the impacts of climate change such as desertification, flooding, and food insecurity—sustainable finance offers a pathway to enhance resilience and promote sustainable growth (Myint, and Krueger, 2025). Nigeria is one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change, primarily due to its dependence on agriculture and natural resources. The country's economy, heavily reliant on oil exports, faces significant risks from climate variability, which affects agricultural productivity, water resources, and overall economic stability. The adverse effects of climate change threaten to exacerbate poverty, increase migration, and challenge national security (Toriola 2021).

Nigeria has vast renewable energy potential, particularly in solar and wind resources. Sustainable climate finance can catalyze investments in these sectors, reducing dependence on fossil fuels, enhancing energy access, and creating job opportunities (FAO. 2022). Agriculture is a cornerstone of Nigeria's economy, employing a significant portion of the population. Climate finance can support sustainable agricultural practices, improve irrigation systems, and promote climate-smart technologies, thereby increasing food security and rural incomes (Toriola 2021).

Despite the potential benefits of sustainable climate finance are significant, Nigeria faces several challenges in realizing these opportunities. There is a substantial gap between the funding required for climate initiatives and the available financial resources (Adhikari, & Safaee-Chalkasra, 2023). Mobilizing both public and private investment is essential for bridging this gap. A clear and supportive policy framework is necessary to guide sustainable investments. This includes incentives for renewable energy, robust environmental regulations, and mechanisms for monitoring and reporting climate finance (Buchner, et al 2023). Developing the necessary institutional capacity and expertise to effectively manage and implement climate finance initiatives is crucial for success. Despite these challenges, Nigeria also has numerous opportunities to leverage sustainable climate finance for economic development. The increasing global focus on sustainability and climate resilience presents a favorable environment for investment in green technologies and initiatives.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite Nigeria's vast potential for sustainable development and its urgent need to address climate change, the integration of sustainable climate finance into the country's economic framework remains inadequate. This shortfall presents significant challenges in mitigating the adverse effects of climate change, which include increased flooding, desertification, and food insecurity. The lack of sufficient funding and investment in renewable energy, climate-resilient infrastructure, and sustainable agricultural practices hampers Nigeria's ability to diversify its economy and reduce its reliance on oil.

Furthermore, the existing policy and regulatory frameworks do not provide the necessary incentives or support for private sector engagement in sustainable initiatives.

As a result, Nigeria faces a dual challenge: the pressing need to combat climate change impacts while striving for economic growth and poverty reduction. This situation is exacerbated by funding gaps, inadequate institutional capacity, and limited awareness of the importance of sustainable climate finance among stakeholders.

Consequently, there is a critical need to assess the effects of sustainable climate finance on economic development in Nigeria, identify barriers to effective implementation, and explore strategies to enhance investment in sustainable practices. Addressing these issues is vital for fostering a resilient economy that can withstand climate impacts while promoting inclusive growth and sustainable development.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Sustainable Climate Finance on Economic Development in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine the effect of Private sector mobilization on Economic Development in Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the international mobilization on Economic Development in Nigeria

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

- i. Private sector mobilization has no significant effect on Economic Development in Nigeria.
- ii. International mobilization has no significant effect on Economic Development in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Sustainable Climate Finance

Climate change represents a critical global challenge requiring substantial financial investment to facilitate mitigation and adaptation efforts. Sustainable climate finance refers to financial flows, both public and private, that support projects aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions and increasing resilience to climate impacts, while aligning with environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria (OECD, 2023). The roots of sustainable climate finance lie in the global response to climate change, particularly through multilateral agreements such as the Paris Agreement 2015. These accords emphasized the necessity for developed countries to provide financial assistance to developing nations to cope with climate-related impacts. According to Buchner et al. (2023), global climate finance flows reached approximately USD 850 billion in 2021, though still far from the estimated USD 4.3 trillion needed annually by 2030 to meet net-zero targets.

Sustainable climate finance is framed within broader concepts such as sustainable development and the green economy. It encompasses investments in renewable energy, energy efficiency, low-carbon technologies, and nature-based solutions. As described by Wang and Zhi (2016), climate finance must also be sustainable in its design, ensuring long-term economic viability and the equitable distribution

of benefits across populations. Multilateral institutions and national governments play a pivotal role in setting the agenda for sustainable climate finance. The future of sustainable climate finance lies in innovation, inclusivity, and systemic transformation. Emerging technologies such as blockchain are being explored to enhance transparency and traceability in climate finance flows (Kshetri, 2022).

Private sector mobilization

Private sector mobilization refers to the strategic process of attracting and utilizing private capital, expertise, and resources to achieve development goals, often in collaboration with public or philanthropic entities. It involves leveraging public or development finance to "crowd in" or incentivize private investment in areas that may be seen as risky or underserved, such as infrastructure, climate action, or sustainable development (Zattler, 2024). Private sector mobilization contributes to job creation, innovation, and capital formation. In emerging markets, where governments often face fiscal constraints, private sector involvement becomes a cornerstone of economic policy. Private sector mobilization is a multifaceted phenomenon shaped by globalization, regulatory changes, and consumer demand. The World Bank (2023) asserts that mobilizing private capital is essential to achieving the \$4 trillion annual investment needed to meet the SDGs. Moreover, private sector mobilization supports industrial development and value chain integration.

In East Africa, partnerships between governments and agribusinesses have improved market access and productivity among smallholder farmers (FAO, 2022). Despite its potential, private sector mobilization faces several challenges. Chief among them are perceived investment risks, regulatory uncertainty, and weak governance structures in many developing countries (Attridge & Engen, 2019). To improve private sector mobilization, scholars and policymakers advocate for stronger regulatory frameworks, risk-sharing mechanisms, and institutional capacity-building. Improved project preparation facilities, such as the Global Infrastructure Facility, can help create viable investment opportunities. Similarly, enhancing transparency and performance evaluation mechanisms can build trust and attract long-term capital (Zattler, 2024).

International mobilization

International mobilization refers to the collective actions, efforts, and strategies undertaken by governments, international organizations, civil society, and other transnational actors to address global challenges such as climate change, human rights violations, health pandemics, armed conflicts, and economic inequality. It plays a critical role in shaping international policy frameworks and fostering global solidarity (Zehra, 2018). The concept of international mobilization draws heavily from social movement theory, transnational advocacy networks, and global governance frameworks. Mobilization at the international level occurs through a variety of mechanisms, including advocacy campaigns, international treaties, multilateral funding, coordinated protests, and digital activism. A common thread is the mobilization of resources, financial, technological, and human, to address transnational

issues. Digital technologies have transformed international mobilization by enabling rapid communication, organizing, and awareness-raising (Zehra, 2018).

Globalization has significantly influenced international mobilization by facilitating the flow of information, resources, and people across borders. International mobilization has also been pivotal in advancing human rights. The #MeToo movement, which gained global traction in 2017, illustrates the power of collective outrage in challenging systemic injustices. By transcending national boundaries, the movement has highlighted the universal nature of gender-based violence, prompting international discourse and policy changes (Gill, 2018). The effectiveness of international mobilization can be hindered by the fragmentation of movements. As different groups pursue diverse agendas, the lack of cohesion can dilute efforts and reduce overall impact (Baiocchi & Ghosh, 2010). The challenge of maintaining unity while accommodating diverse perspectives remains a critical concern for activists engaged in international mobilization.

Economic Development

Economic development refers to a continuous enhancement in the material welfare of society. Economic development is a wider concept than economic growth. Apart from the growth of national income, it includes changes in social, cultural, political, as well as economic factors, which contribute to material progress. It contains changes in resource supplies, in the rate of capital formation, in the size and composition of the population, in technology, skills, and efficiency, and institutional and organizational set-up (Panth, 2021). Long-term increases in a nation's net national product are the result of a series of interconnected changes in the basic elements of supply and demand structure that make up economic development. It entails both qualitative and quantitative economic growth in a nation (Toriola, 2021).

Schumpeter defines economic development as a discontinuous and spontaneous change in the stationary state that permanently modifies and displaces the previously existing equilibrium state, whereas Friedman defines it as an innovative process that results in the structural transformation of the social system (Panth, 2021). In general, economic development is understood to be the structural change of an economy through the introduction of more modern and mechanized technology to raise employment, labor productivity, earnings, and the population's standard of living. To support economic change, infrastructure upgrades as well as social, political, and institutional aspects should accompany economic progress (Myint and Krueger 2016). By creating more jobs, raising wages, improving goods and services, and utilizing the newest production technology, economic development is thought to be crucial for a nation to combat poverty.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder theory, pioneered by Freeman (1984), posits that a company's success is intertwined with the well-being of all its stakeholders, not just shareholders. Stakeholders encompass a broad range of

individuals and groups affected by or able to affect an organization's activities, including employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and financiers (Freeman and Dmytriiev, 2017). In the context of private sector mobilization, stakeholder theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how businesses can strategically engage with societal challenges while creating value for all involved (Gaonkar and Chetty 2020).

Silva-Santisteban (2021) asserts that Stakeholder theory challenges the traditional shareholder-centric view by asserting that businesses have responsibilities extending beyond profit maximization. Key principles include: Interdependence, Multiple Objectives, Ethical Considerations, and Stakeholder Engagement. By embracing a stakeholder-oriented approach, private sector actors can enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of their mobilization efforts. Stakeholder theory provides a framework for understanding the dynamics within PPPs, which involve collaboration between public and private entities, also align their strategies with the SDGs, addressing global challenges such as poverty, inequality, and climate change (Silva-Santisteban, 2021).

World-Systems Theory

World-Systems Theory, developed by Immanuel Wallerstein, provides a framework for understanding the global economy as an interconnected system characterized by core, semi-periphery, and periphery countries. This theory posits that the world system is structured hierarchically, with core nations dominating and exploiting peripheral nations for resources and labor. World-Systems Theory helps explain the dynamics of transnational social movements, global inequalities, and the political relationships between nations (Chase-Dunn and Grell-Brisk, 2019). World-Systems Theory sheds light on the political relationships and conflicts between nations. The hierarchical structure of the global system contributes to tensions between core and periphery countries over issues like trade, aid, and debt. International mobilization may involve efforts to promote peace, democracy, and human rights in regions affected by these conflicts. When the world system is far from equilibrium, small social mobilizations can have very great repercussions. While the theory has faced criticisms, it remains a significant perspective for analyzing global issues and promoting international mobilization efforts (Fiveable, 2024).

2.3 Empirical Reviews

Musyoka (2014) conducted a study to investigate how resource mobilization strategies influence the performance of community-based organizations (CBOs) in developing contexts, with a particular focus on Tseikuru Sub-County, Kitui County, Kenya. The study aims to examine the effect of various resource mobilization strategies on the performance of CBOs in Tseikuru and identify which strategies such as fundraising, volunteer engagement, partnership development, and strategic planning best enhance CBO effectiveness and project outcomes. Descriptive survey research design was utilized in this study. The results revealed that well-rounded resource mobilization combining strategic planning, proactive

fundraising, volunteer mobilization, and meaningful partnerships, positively drives CBO performance in rural Kenyan settings.

Averchenkova (2017) conducted a study on engaging the private sector and mobilizing private finance through mitigation actions in developing countries across Asia. The study aims to provide an overview of key issues in engaging private-sector actors in mitigation in developing nations, analyze the motivations and barriers for different private players regarding climate mitigation finance, and identify practical opportunities and showcase implementation experiences from national mitigation efforts (NAMAs). The study employed a qualitative review combining conceptual discussion with analysis of practical case studies. The results revealed that while private capital is recognized as crucial for climate mitigation in developing countries, its practical deployment via NAMAs remains underdeveloped.

Zehra (2018) conducted a study to explore resource mobilization among informal entrepreneurs, focusing on the event planning industry in Pakistan. The study aims to understand how informal entrepreneurs mobilize resources, such as knowledge, materials, ideas, and contacts, during the founding and early growth phases and to integrate the resource mobilization perspective with social and human capital theory, identifying how these forms of capital support resource access in informal ventures. The study employed a qualitative multiple-case approach. The results revealed that rather than competing, these entrepreneurs rely on collaborative networks, with social and human capital acting as key facilitators.

Adhikari & Safae-Chalkasra (2023) conducted a study to examine how to mobilize private sector investment for climate action, focusing on enhancing ambition and scaling up implementation of climate adaptation efforts across Asia, Latin America, and Sub-Saharan Africa. The study aims to fill knowledge gaps on barriers, risks, and opportunities associated with private-sector climate investment and to determine conditions under which different private actors (SMEs, MNCs, B-corps, impact investors) are motivated or hindered in funding climate adaptation. The study utilized a qualitative case-study approach. The results revealed that effective mobilization hinges on public-private collaboration, targeted financial instruments (like blended finance), and improved knowledge and policy ecosystems, especially in developing regions.

3. Methodology

This study adopts a quantitative research design to investigate the effect of Sustainable Climate Finance on Economic Development in Nigeria. The quantitative approach provides a structured means of collecting and analyzing numerical data to assess the influence of climate finance on economic indicators such as GDP growth, job creation, and poverty reduction. This design supports objective evaluation and statistical generalization of findings from a defined group of stakeholders actively involved in climate-related financial interventions. The target population consists of approximately 1,000 individuals involved in climate finance and economic development across Nigeria. These include

professionals from the Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Environment, Central Bank of Nigeria, commercial banks, investment institutions, climate-focused NGOs, and academic researchers.

A sample size of 278 respondents was determined using Yamane's formula (1967) at a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. Purposive sampling was employed to ensure inclusion of respondents with relevant expertise. Primary data was gathered through a structured questionnaire, using a 5-point Likert scale to measure variables such as awareness, accessibility, effectiveness, and impact of sustainable climate finance. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis to evaluate the relationship between sustainable climate finance and economic development indicators. Analytical tools such as SPSS were utilized. Instrument reliability was established through a pilot study with a Cronbach's Alpha threshold of 0.70, while content validity was ensured through expert review.

The regression equation is $Y = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \mu_i$ will be applied, where Y represents economic development, x_1 and x_2 private sector mobilization and international mobilization, respectively, a is the constant b_1 and b_2 are the coefficients of the predictor's variables and μ_i is the error term. To ensure the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot study will be conducted with 78 respondents, with adjustments made based on feedback. Reliability and validity were assessed using Cronbach's alpha and Average variance extracted, aiming for a value above 0.70 respectively to confirm internal consistency and validity. Ethical considerations included obtaining informed consent and ensuring participant confidentiality.

4. Results

This section presents the results of data analysis and the discussion of findings based on the objectives of the study. Specifically, this section covers the demographic characteristics of the respondents, descriptive statistics of the variables, reliability analysis, hypothesis testing, and discussions of the findings about existing literature.

Demographic characteristics of the Respondents

The demographic information of the respondents includes gender, age, educational qualification, and years of work experience. These characteristics provide context to better understand the perspectives of the respondents.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the respondent (n=264)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	165	62.5%
Female	99	37.5%
Age		
18-30 years	32	12.1%
31-40 years	76	28.8%
41-50 years	67	25.4%
Above 50 years	91	34.5%
Educational Qualification		
Diploma	30	11.4%
Bachelor's Degree	140	53%
Master's Degree	68	25.8%
Others	44	16.7%
Marital Status		
Single	73	27.7%
Married	182	68.9%
Divorced/Widowed	09	3.4%

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the 264 respondents who participated in the study. In terms of gender distribution, a majority of the respondents were male (62.5%), while females accounted for 37.5%. This suggests a relatively male-dominated respondent base, which may reflect broader gender representation trends in climate finance and economic development sectors. The age distribution shows that the largest group of respondents (34.5%) were above 50 years, followed by 31–40 years (28.8%), and 41–50 years (25.4%). A smaller proportion (12.1%) were within the 18–30 years age bracket. This indicates that the sample is largely composed of middle-aged and older professionals, potentially reflecting their more active involvement or leadership in policy, finance, or development roles. Regarding educational qualification, over half of the respondents (53%) held a Bachelor's degree, while 25.8% had a Master's degree. Others included Diploma holders (11.4%) and other qualifications (16.7%), showing that the sample is generally well-educated. In terms of marital status, 68.9% of respondents were married, while 27.7% were single and 3.4% were divorced or widowed. These demographics suggest that the study gathered insights from a mature, educated, and professionally diverse group of individuals.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the responses to each variable which include collaborative goal-setting, employee empowerment, and organizational development.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Private sector mobilization	3.021	1.01
International mobilization on mobilization	3.173	1.28
Economic Development	3.376	1.47

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for the key variables in the study. The mean score for Private Sector Mobilization is 3.021 with a standard deviation of 1.01, indicating a moderate level of agreement among respondents on the involvement of the private sector in sustainable climate finance, with relatively low variability in responses. International Mobilization recorded a slightly higher mean of 3.173 and a standard deviation of 1.28, suggesting a moderate to fairly strong perception of international efforts and support in mobilizing climate finance, but with more variation in respondent views compared to the private sector. The mean for Economic Development is 3.376, the highest among the three variables, with a standard deviation of 1.47. This implies that respondents generally perceive a positive link between climate finance activities and economic development outcomes in Nigeria, although the higher standard deviation indicates greater differences in individual assessments.

Reliability and Validity Test

The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha to ensure internal consistency.

Table 3: Reliability and Validity Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE
Private sector mobilization	0.71	0.54
International mobilization on mobilization	0.85	0.66
Economic Development	0.79	0.51

Table 3 summarizes the reliability and validity results for the key constructs used in this study. Cronbach's Alpha values for all variables exceed the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, indicating strong internal consistency. Specifically, Private Sector Mobilization has a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.71, International Mobilization shows a high reliability score of 0.85, and Economic Development records 0.79. These values confirm that the items under each construct are consistently measuring their intended dimensions. Regarding convergent validity, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs are above the recommended minimum of 0.50. Private Sector Mobilization has an AVE of 0.54, International Mobilization stands at 0.66, and Economic Development records an AVE of 0.51. These results indicate that a significant proportion of variance in the indicators is explained by the underlying latent constructs, thereby confirming that the measurement model demonstrates acceptable convergent validity. Overall, the reliability and validity test results affirm that the

instrument used for data collection is both reliable and valid for assessing the effect of sustainable climate finance—through private and international mobilization—on economic development in Nigeria.

Regression Results

Regression analysis which is an inferential statistics approach was employed to test the study's hypotheses. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to assess the effect of collaborative goal-setting and employee empowerment on organizational development.

Table 4: Regression Output

Model 1	Coefficient	F-statistic	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Durban-Watson
PSM	.462 [.000]	99.381 [.000]	.698	.691	.400
IMM	.347 [.000]				
Constant	3.41 [.002]				

PSM= Private sector mobilization; IMM=International mobilization on mobilization; [] represent p-value.

Table 4 presents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the effect of Private Sector Mobilization (PSM) and International Mobilization (IMM) on Economic Development in Nigeria. The model demonstrates a strong overall fit, with an R-Square value of 0.698, indicating that approximately 69.8% of the variance in Economic Development is explained jointly by PSM and IMM. The Adjusted R-Square of 0.691 confirms that the model remains robust even after adjusting for the number of predictors.

The regression coefficients show that both predictors have a statistically significant and positive influence on Economic Development. Specifically, Private Sector Mobilization (PSM) has a coefficient of 0.462 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that a one-unit increase in PSM is associated with a 0.462-unit increase in Economic Development, holding other variables constant. Similarly, International Mobilization (IMM) has a coefficient of 0.347 and a p-value of 0.000, signifying a significant positive relationship. The constant term (intercept) is 3.41, also significant ($p = 0.002$), suggesting the baseline level of economic development when both predictors are at zero. The F-statistic value of 99.381 ($p = 0.000$) confirms that the overall regression model is statistically significant, meaning the independent variables together reliably predict Economic Development. However, the Durbin-Watson statistic is 0.400, which is considerably below the recommended threshold (~ 2.0), indicating the possible presence of positive autocorrelation in the residuals. This suggests that the model may benefit from further diagnostic testing or adjustment to address serial correlation.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: Private sector mobilization has no significant effect on Economic development in Nigeria.

H₀₂: International mobilization on mobilization has no significant effect on economic development in Nigeria.

Decision Rule

For H_{01} : If the p-value for private sector mobilization is ≤ 0.05 , reject H_{01} and conclude that private sector mobilization has a significant effect on economic development in Nigeria. Otherwise, do not reject H_{01} .

For H_{02} : If the p-value for international mobilization on mobilization is ≤ 0.05 , reject H_{02} and conclude that international mobilization on mobilization has a significant effect economic development in Nigeria. Otherwise, do not reject H_{02} .

Table 5: Diagnostic Test

Diagnostic Test	Method Used	Test Statistic	P-value
Normality Test	Shapiro-Wilk Test	.815	.072
	Kolmogorov -Smirnov Test	.189	.056
Multicollinearity Test	Variance Inflation factor (VIF)	$X_1=2.15$; $X_2=1.98$	===
Heteroscedasticity Test	Breusch-Pagan Test	$\chi^2 = 4.27$	0.342

X_1 =Private sector mobilization; X_2 =International mobilization on mobilization. Outcome variable: Economic development

Table 5 presents the results of diagnostic tests conducted to validate the assumptions underlying the multiple regression model. Normality of residuals was assessed using both the Shapiro-Wilk Test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. The Shapiro-Wilk test yielded a test statistic of 0.815 with a p-value of 0.072, while the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test gave a statistic of 0.189 and a p-value of 0.056. In both cases, the p-values are greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that the residuals are approximately normally distributed, and the assumption of normality is not violated. The Multicollinearity Test was performed using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values. The VIF for Private Sector Mobilization (X_1) is 2.15, and for International Mobilization (X_2) is 1.98. Since both values are below the critical threshold of 5, there is no evidence of multicollinearity between the independent variables, confirming that they are sufficiently independent of one another. To test for heteroscedasticity, the Breusch-Pagan Test was applied, yielding a Chi-square statistic of 4.27 and a p-value of 0.342. As the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result indicates that there is no significant heteroscedasticity in the model. This means the variance of the residuals is constant across observations, satisfying another key assumption of linear regression. There is a statistically significant positive effect of private sector mobilization on the economic development in Nigeria, having a coefficient value of .462 with p-value (0.000). There is a statistically significant positive effect of international mobilization on mobilization on the economic development in Nigeria, having a coefficient value of .347 with p-value (0.000).

5. Conclusion

Sustainable climate finance plays a pivotal role in shaping Nigeria's economic development by addressing the dual challenges of climate change and economic growth. The mobilization of private sector investment is particularly critical, as it not only facilitates the funding of renewable energy projects and climate-resilient infrastructure but also fosters innovation and job creation in green industries. By engaging the private sector, Nigeria can diversify its economy away from oil dependency, thus enhancing resilience to climate impacts and promoting sustainable development.

Moreover, international mobilization of climate finance is equally significant for Nigeria's economic trajectory. Support from developed countries and international organizations provides essential resources that enable Nigeria to implement effective climate strategies. This financial assistance can help strengthen local capacities, improve infrastructure, and enhance adaptive measures against climate risks.

In summary, both private and international mobilization of sustainable climate finance are instrumental in driving economic development in Nigeria. By leveraging these financial resources, Nigeria can not only mitigate the impacts of climate change but also foster inclusive growth, create jobs, and build a resilient economy capable of thriving in a changing climate. As the nation navigates this complex landscape, the strategic integration of sustainable climate finance into its development agenda will be crucial for ensuring a sustainable and prosperous future. The study concluded that Sustainable Climate Finance has significant effect on Economic Development in Nigeria.

Recommendations

To effectively harness the potential of sustainable climate finance for economic development in Nigeria, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. The government should develop policies that provide tax incentives, subsidies, and grants to encourage private sector investment in renewable energy and sustainable projects. This will help reduce perceived risks and attract more capital.
- ii. The government should actively seek funding from international climate finance mechanisms such as the Green Climate Fund and the Global Environment Facility. Nigeria should prioritize projects that align with global climate goals to increase eligibility for funding.

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